

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

LOGICAL STRUCTURING TRAINING CONTENT TOPICS METHODS OF NUMERICAL INTEGRATION OF DETERMINED INTEGRALS

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Abstract

This article is focused on various aspects of the development of logically structured educational technology. The levels of logical structuring of the teaching content of the topic are considered when implementing a structural-modular approach to organizing the educational process. The problems of identifying structural elements are discussed in the content of education and the formation of a modular program.

Keywords: algorithm, structuring of educational material, logical module, modular technology, accelerated learning.

Currently, the search, development and implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process are actively underway to satisfy modern society's demands for flexible, multi-purpose and effective training programs. Interest in logically structured modular technology is due to its significant advantages: the technological, structural and content flexibility of modular educational programs, the possibility of widespread use of information and communication technologies to individualize students' independent work, the complexity, efficiency and objectivity of assessing students' educational achievements, the applicability of technology in organizations of all types educational activities of students.

Modular learning is based on the sequential mastery of the content of integral units of the curriculum structure - modules. The modularity of the structure can be considered as the basis and sign of a systemic organization. Let us note that in pedagogical theory and practice there are different points of view on understanding the module and the technology of its construction. In this regard, it is necessary to clarify the meaning of this term in terms of the problematic aspects of the issues under consideration. From our point of view, a module is a functionally independent technological unit that includes all components of the methodological system (goals, content of training, organizational forms and methods of training, teaching tools, monitoring and evaluation of learning results) [1,2,3].

Let us consider the formation of an algorithmically structured training topic on methods of numerical integration of definite integrals in the discipline "Design of Algorithms" based on a subject-based approach to determining the structure of educational content, as well as determining the goals and methods of teaching. The components of the module are logically structured educational elements (UE), which are content- and functionally interconnected and interdependent units of structure. The content of an educational element can be represented by smaller portions of educational information - educational elements of the second and third order (Fig. 1).

Now we are creating a semantic graph for presenting the educational elements of the modules, for example, for module 1 of the rectangle method (Fig. 2). For students, graphical diagrams of modules give a clear idea of the volume of educational information and the order of its development in the module. The graph of the logical structure of a module reflects not only the composition and interconnection of educational elements, but also the dynamics of the learning process, as well as the sequence of stages of the teacher's educational activity. In the general case, the graph corresponds to a module, and its vertices correspond to educational elements (EE) and serial numbers of classroom sessions [2,3].

Fig.1. Modular-structured training on the topic of numerical integration of definite integrals. LR method of left rectangles; RR method of right rectangles; MR method of average rectangles.

Fig.2. Semantic graph of module-1. Left, right and middle rectangle methods.

Based on a system-activity approach to identifying structural elements, a modular training system can be designed in the form of educational and methodological manuals (for students or teachers) for studying theoretical foundations, for performing laboratory, practical,

coursework, and individual ones. test tasks, etc. developed on the basis of a modular structure.

Therefore, each module has a content structure, in which we have identified the following components: control, coordination, information and methodological and monitoring parts (Fig. 3).

Fig.3. Structural components of the module content.

Modeling the content of modules for presentation in various educational media (brochures, electronic publications, etc.), which requires deep transformations and formalization of information, represents an internal plan for structuring the content of education.

The developed modular-structured teaching methodology contributes to the acquisition of the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies according to individual student learning trajectories. Such a concept will require universities to plan and organize the educational process in such a way that the desires of students and the capabilities of teachers, rather than plans, come first. This approach imitates the laws of the market - both teachers offer a set of courses, and students express a desire to study them, and students put forward requests for the formation of disciplines with certain competencies and content, and teachers develop these courses.

The modular-structured teaching methodology is intended to increase the effectiveness of control activities for mastering the material on the main issues and sections of the discipline "Design of Algorithms" (or for self-control of students [4]) when organizing the ed-

ucational process, taking into account individual learning trajectories.

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